

Survey on viewing video clips with machine-translated subtitles

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Participation in this research is voluntary. You may stop responding to the questionnaire at any point, in which case none of your answers will be saved or used in the study. When you press Send at the end of the questionnaire, your answers will be added to the research data, and it will no longer be possible to remove them. In other words, by pressing Send you are giving permission for your answers to be used in the study.

If you have any questions about the study, you can contact the researchers Tiina Tuominen, Kaisa Vitikainen or Maarit Koponen at the addresses given below.

Many thanks for contributing to our study!

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*Required

1. I have received sufficient information about the research and handling of research data, and I am willing to take part in the study. *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

2. I am at least 18 years old. *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

Information
about you

In this section, we would like you to share some details about yourself that are relevant to the study.

3. What is your age? *

Mark only one oval.

18–29

30–44

45–59

Over 59

I prefer not to say

4. What is the highest level of education you have completed? *

Mark only one oval.

- I have not completed any level of education
- Primary education
- Secondary education
- Vocational qualification
- Some studies at a university or other institute of higher education, but no degree
- Undergraduate degree (e.g. BA, BSc)
- Postgraduate degree (e.g. MA, MSc)
- Doctoral degree or higher
- Other: _____

5. How well do you understand spoken Finnish? *

Mark only one oval.

- Not at all
- I understand some words and phrases in simple spoken Finnish
- I understand the main points in simple spoken Finnish
- I understand the majority of simple spoken Finnish
- I understand even complex spoken Finnish quite well
- I usually have no difficulty understanding any kind of spoken Finnish

6. Do you live or have you ever lived in Finland? *

Mark only one oval.

- I currently live in Finland and have lived in Finland for less than a year
- I currently live in Finland and have lived in Finland for 1–5 years
- I currently live in Finland and have lived in Finland for 6–10 years
- I currently live in Finland and have lived in Finland for more than 10 years
- I do not live in Finland, but I have previously lived in Finland for less than a year
- I do not live in Finland, but I have previously lived in Finland for 1–5 years
- I do not live in Finland, but I have previously lived in Finland for 6–10 years
- I do not live in Finland, but I have previously lived in Finland for more than 10 years
- I have never lived in Finland

7. How often do you watch foreign-language programmes with English subtitles? *

Mark only one oval.

- Never
- Rarely (a few times a year or less)
- Occasionally (every month or nearly every month)
- Often (every week)

Video
1

Please watch the video clip below and then answer the questions related to the video. If you want to, you can watch the video more than once, but you can answer the questions based on just a single viewing.

Video 1

8. Did you understand what the topic of the video was and what was said about that topic?

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Not at all	☐	Yes, completely				

9. What is the Patria AMV? *

Mark only one oval.

- A weapons system used by Rangers in the battlefield
- An armoured military transport vehicle
- The official name of the PASI vehicle
- A mobile military intelligence system
- I don't know

10. What was going on in the office in Vienna at the beginning of the clip? *

Mark only one oval.

- Patria's Austrian agent was losing patience with Patria.
- Patria's Slovenian clients were attempting to deceive the Austrian agent.
- Patria was pressuring its Slovenian clients to pay for their purchases.
- The Slovenian visitors were demanding money from Patria.
- I don't know

15. In comparison to an average experience of viewing a subtitled programme, how well did you manage to read the subtitles all the way through? *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Considerably worse than usual Considerably better than usual

16. In comparison to an average experience of viewing a subtitled programme, how much mental effort did you have to invest to learn new information from the clip? *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Considerably more than usual Considerably less than usual

Video
2

Please watch the video clip below and then answer the questions related to the video. If you want to, you can watch the video more than once, but you can answer the questions based on just a single viewing.

Video 2

17. Did you understand what the topic of the video was and what was said about that topic?

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Not at all	☐	Yes, completely				

18. Why do towns in Eastern Finland want a faster train connection to Helsinki? *

Mark only one oval.

- They hope it will bring in some much-needed investments to remote areas
- They hope it means the state is willing to invest in public transport
- They hope it will bring in larger numbers of tourists
- They hope it will slow down population decline
- I don't know

19. How would the new rail connection be financed? *

Mark only one oval.

- A new state-owned company would pay for it
- Local municipalities would invest in the project
- The increasing passenger numbers would cover the costs
- No one knows yet
- I don't know

20. What is the current status of the project? *

Mark only one oval.

- The plans have been made and construction will start soon
- It is currently in the planning stage
- No decisions have been made yet
- The company is committed to completing the project by 2030
- I don't know

Your views on the video and the subtitles

21. Was the video pleasant to watch? *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Not at all pleasant	☐	Very pleasant				

22. How useful were the subtitles in helping you understand the clip? *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Not at all usefull	☐	Very useful				

23. Did the information in the subtitles seem accurate to you? *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
No, not at all accurate	☐	Yes, completely accurate				

27. Under what circumstances could you imagine watching videos on platforms such as news websites or social media with subtitles like these? *

Mark only one oval.

- Any time automatic subtitles are available for a foreign-language video that interests me.
- Only if I cannot easily find similar videos or information on the same topic in a language I understand.
- Only if the topic is exceptionally interesting or important and there is no information available about it in a language I understand.
- Never
- Other: _____

28. If you could choose either automatic subtitles that were available immediately or human-made subtitles that were available a couple of days later, which one would you choose? *

Mark only one oval.

- I would definitely choose the automatic subtitles.
- I would choose the automatic subtitles in most cases.
- I could take either one.
- I would choose the human-made subtitles in most cases.
- I would definitely choose the human-made subtitles.
- Other: _____

29. Can you think of some situations or some types of videos with which you could use automatic subtitles like the ones you saw in the video clips?

30. If you do not think these subtitles were good enough, what are some things that should be improved in order for you to use them?

Other comments and feedback

31. If you have any other comments about the subtitles you saw or about using automatic subtitles and machine translation, you can share them here.

32. This is where you can give feedback on this questionnaire.

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